

EVALUATING MULTI-MATERIAL-CONCEPTS REGARDING TECHNICAL, ECOLOGICAL AND ECONOMICAL PROPERTIES

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ABSTRACT

Laws regarding emissions, especially CO₂, have tightened, and vehicle size is increasing. Consequently, lightweight vehicle design is essential to decrease emissions. Conventional materials and constructions methods are reaching their limits, leading to the consideration of lightweight materials such as fibre reinforced plastics for mass production. The combination of both fibre reinforced plastics and metallic materials is called multi-material, or hybrid design.

Therefore, the “BMBF Forschungscampus Open Hybrid LabFactory” aims to develop new manufacturing technologies for economic and multifunctional lightweight design. The Open Hybrid LabFactory is a public private partnership where both companies and universities collaborate in research. One major project of this corporation is the “MultiMaK2”, aiming to develop design and evaluation tools to use case specific ecologically optimised multi-material vehicle components. Ecology, lightweight design and economy are conflicting development goals, thus compromises and an assessment of the ecological, economical, and lightweight properties are compulsory. Moreover, various component concepts need to be compared. In order to determine these properties and to compare various component concepts a software tool is being developed. This tool contains empirical and analytical formula estimating the mentioned properties and various evaluation methods to compare the above mentioned concepts. The implemented formula determine mechanical properties such as weight and stiffness as well as economical properties for which production time and estimated costs are common examples. In addition, failure criteria for isotropic materials, fibre reinforced composites and the adhesive joining are implemented. After the determination of the properties the user is able to evaluate the concepts and compare the final results with each other. As a result, the software tool displays a radar chart with the technical, ecological and economical properties.

In order to extend the future scope of the project, the software tool will be extended by adding more detailed calculation methods. Furthermore, the tool might be connected to CAD systems.

1 INTRODUCTION

The amount of customer demands regarding vehicle comfort, safety or driving dynamics are rising continuously. In the past, these demands led to increasing vehicle weight. However, this trend has stopped by developing new vehicle concepts and by using lightweight materials (light metals, high-strength steel or fibre reinforced plastics). Thus the vehicle weight is kept at a constant or slightly decreasing level, especially in vehicles with conventional drivetrains. Nevertheless, this lightweight trend must be continued, taking into account the future automotive standards in quality, ecology and economy. [1]

In this paper, the combination of both, fibre reinforced plastics and metallic materials, is called multi-material or hybrid design. The combination of fibre reinforced plastics with steel or steel aluminium structures is currently not available for mass production. This is caused by the high cost of fibre materials. In addition, the process time of producing fibre reinforced components is high.

Figure 1: Strategy to enable new lightweight potential in the automotive industry. [2]

Thus the production of mixed structures with fibre reinforced components seems to be more suitable for mass production. Figure 1 illustrates present vehicle body concepts considering the producible quantities and points out possible ways to weight-optimised lightweight vehicle body concepts for large scale production. [2]

The usage of multi-material design influences the vehicle concept. Furthermore, the production of lightweight materials requires a larger amount of energy and resources. Therefore, the usage of carbon fibre reinforced plastics amortises ecologically not until 85,000 km to 130,000 km have been travelled [3].

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2 STATE OF RESEARCH

The state of research is divided into two sections: The first section deals with the design of multi-material components in automotive applications while the second section summarises methods requirements design of components in multi-material-design.

2.1 Design of multi-material components in automotive applications

Conventional materials and constructions methods like geometry optimisation and material substitution are reaching their limits. This is why new lightweight design strategies are taken into account. A promising approach is the multi-material-design which is characterised by load and function specific interaction of different materials within one component. There are various applications and perspectives for components in multi-material design in the automotive industry. In

most cases, the application of plastics for large scale production is limited to components with low level exposure (e.g. interior trim, fenders, tailgates, front-end modules). Nowadays, higher loaded plastic components are implemented as a result of using of short fibres as composites in large scale production. For continuous fibre reinforced plastic parts, which meet or exceed the properties of steel materials, applicable manufacturing processes are limited to small quantities. Thermoplastic prepregs such as organic sheets are only used for expensive vehicle classes for example in the rear seat structure and the crash management system (front and rear bumper bracket) of the BMW M3. For structural components in multi-material design new vehicle concepts (e.g. BMW i Concept) are pursued which require novel assembly process chains and infrastructures.

Other applications aim for material substitution for large-scale production with the goal of conventional vehicle concepts and components (e.g. SuperLIGHT-Car) [5]. Application of multi-material-design influences the shape of components and entire products, which in turn affects the production processes. An integration of the multi-material-components in the current process chains is indispensable to achieve large scale producibility. In this case, the joining and production technologies affect the component's requirements significantly. The resulting complex relations are a challenging task for the designing engineer of components in multi-material-design.

The multi-material-design has great potential for weight reduction in vehicle design, but there are currently no manufacturing processes for large-scale production available. Moreover, the design of multi-material-components needs to be facilitated due to the complex relations of technical ecological and economical development goals.

2.2 Methods for requirements design of components in multi-material-design

Requirements management is the basis of the holistic design of components. The requirement compatible design of components therefore represents one of the most important steps in the overall development of multi-material components. The determination, processing, distribution and review of requirements is carried out with respect to the entire product life-cycle. In order to control the growing complexity an appropriate requirement model is necessary which allows tracking the origin and dependencies of the requirements considering different departments and the entire life-cycle [6].

There are various approaches for determination of requirements, such as questionnaires [7] and checklists [8]. In addition, the computer-aided tool "IKonzept" according to Nehuis [9] provides the opportunity to map the dependencies between the product (component) and its surroundings (systems influenced by the component or influencing the component). All requirements need to be determined, processed and distributed using computer-aided systems. Requirements include functions and features of the component for instance mechanical properties. Accompanying the methodological component design, the review of requirements is carried out. The generated functions and features of a component must be continuously compared with the set of requirements. One way of quantifying the characteristics of a component concept and thus carry out the review of requirements, is for instance, Excel-based tools or computer algebra systems, such as MATLAB.

Requirements management is crucial for the holistic design of components in multi-material design for large-scale quantities in the automotive industry, since the development is distributed among diverse departments and therefore, a close integration of these departments must be given. In addition, the component's properties need to be determined continuously on the basis of analytical or empirical models in order to evaluate whether the components meet the requirements. To assist the developer in these activities, a methodical assistance in the development of components in multi-material design, especially in the early phase of the development process is compulsory [10-11]. To achieve this objective, the approach is a software tool for the evaluation of component concepts in multi-material-design.

3. METHODOLOGICAL APPROACH FOR EVALUATION OF CONCEPTS

For carrying out an evaluation of competitive components, a holistic evaluation method is necessary to assess whether the components meet the requirements. There are various methods available, such as value analysis and cost-benefit analysis. For every evaluation method the relevant development goals must to be defined, structured and optionally weighted.

Figure 2: Excerpt of the structure of development goals and sub-goals

There are several development goals using a holistic approach on components in multi-material-design. An excerpt of those development goals and sub-goals is shown in figure 2. The overall goal an economic and sustainable lightweight design needs good economical, ecological and technical properties. These can be divided into sub-goals that are, amongst others, costs, global warming potential, stiffness and weight. For evaluating these properties, analytical as well as empirical and numerical calculations have to be conducted. In order to fulfil this task a software tool is being developed which contains by now empirical and analytical formula in order to estimate the mentioned properties and various evaluation methods to compare the concepts. The implemented formula determine mechanical properties such as weight and stiffness along with economical properties like production time and estimated costs. Furthermore, failure criteria for isotropic materials, fibre reinforced composites and the adhesive joining are implemented.

3.1 Software concept

The developed software-tool is MATLAB-based and is implemented as stand-alone solution with a graphical user interface (figure 3). The software guides the user from the component definition to the evaluation criteria and the comparison of different concepts in contrast to the requirements.

Every concept evaluation takes place in the context of a project and therefore the evaluation can be saved and continued at a later time. After the definition of the project, the user defines up to three component concepts. The third step contains the selection of the evaluation criteria and sub-criteria according to the development goals.

Figure 3: Graphical User Interface

The predefined list of evaluation criteria currently includes the following categories that summarise multiple component properties:

- Weight
- Stiffness
- Quasistatic Strength
- Fatigue Strength
- Crash Properties
- Acoustics, Optics and Odour
- Temperature Resistance
- Media Resistance
- Life Cycle Assessment
- Costs
- Producibility

Afterwards, the user enters the relevant parameter (e.g. material, geometry etc.) of the component concepts whereby the relevant parameter differ according to the selected criteria. Each component concept consists of up to three monolithic bodies that are assembled and joined together. The assembly of these bodies, their geometry and material defines for instance the component's stiffness. The

relations between the component parameter and the evaluation criteria are qualitatively shown in figure 4.

Figure 4: System of relations between component parameter and evaluated criteria

Followed by the definition of the component parameter, the evaluation method (by now cost-benefit analysis with different rating scales) is selected and the criteria and sub-criteria are optionally weighted against each other based on the comparison of pairs. Afterwards, the actual calculation of component properties is conducted.

The evaluation is done by the user based on a comparison of the calculated properties. The usage of value functions, which correlate the component properties with an evaluation, have been discussed but seem to be rather inappropriate because a general approach on evaluating component concepts desired. After the evaluation of the component concepts, the results are visualised via radar charts.

3.2 Software architecture

The program has a modular design for an easy extension by new modules. The software consists of a central management module, supplement modules, saving modules, calculation modules and various data sets. The central management module hosts the GUI, manages all data and starts the other modules. The supplement modules undertake amongst others the component definition, the evaluation and the weighting of criteria. The saving modules enable the user to save and load projects, components and user profiles with user-specific evaluation criteria and weighting. The calculation modules determine the component properties. The data sets store specific information about material, production processes and joining processes, this reference data assures a high reproducibility and an easy usage of the tool. If individual users evaluate different component concepts in context of the same project, each user operates with the same evaluation criteria and weighting. Moreover, the reference data assures that every calculation is conducted with comparable data.

4 EVALUATIONS AND COMPARISON

After the determination of the properties the user is able to evaluate the concepts and compare the evaluations with each other each other. The final evaluation screen summarises the user's evaluation whereby the tool displays the overall evaluation as well as the criteria evaluation with and without consideration of the weighting. In addition to the values the significance of the competitive concepts are displayed. Besides, the tabular presentation of the evaluation radar charts are available.

Teilziele		Multimaterial				Stahl				Aluminium			
Nr.	Gew.	Ungew. Wert	Gew. Wert	Ungew. Wertigkeit	Gew. Wertigkeit	Ungew. Wert	Gew. Wert	Ungew. Wertigkeit	Gew. Wertigkeit	Ungew. Wert	Gew. Wert	Ungew. Wertigkeit	Gew. Wertigkeit
1. Gewicht	0.14049	4/4	0.56198	1	0.1405	1/4	0.1405	0.25	0.03512	3/4	0.42149	0.75	0.10537
2. Steifigkeit	0.14049	0/12	0	0	0	0/12	0	0	0	0/12	0	0	0
3. Quasistatische Festigkeit	0.14049	0/24	0	0	0	0/24	0	0	0	0/24	0	0	0
4. Dauer- und Betriebsfestigkeit	0.14049	0/24	0	0	0	0/24	0	0	0	0/24	0	0	0
5. Crasheigenschaften	0.14049	0/12	0	0	0	0/12	0	0	0	0/12	0	0	0
6. Akustik, Optik und Geruch	0.04958	7/12	0.1157	0.58333	0.02893	11/12	0.18182	0.91667	0.04545	9/12	0.14876	0.75	0.03719
7. Temperatureinfluss	0.04132	4/20	0.03306	0.2	0.00826	3/20	0.02479	0.15	0.0062	3/20	0.02479	0.15	0.0062
8. Medien- und Strahlungseinfluss	0.04958	5/20	0.04959	0.25	0.0124	6/20	0.0595	0.3	0.01488	4/20	0.03967	0.2	0.00992
9. Energieaufwand	0.04958	11/12	0.18182	0.91667	0.04545	7/12	0.1157	0.58333	0.02893	8/12	0.13223	0.66667	0.03306
10. Kosten	0.05785	2/12	0.03857	0.16667	0.00964	6/12	0.1157	0.5	0.02893	7/12	0.13499	0.58333	0.03375
11. Großserieneignung	0.04958	2/8	0.04959	0.25	0.0124	4/8	0.09917	0.5	0.02479	3/8	0.07438	0.375	0.0186
		Ungewichteter Gesamtwert				Ungewichteter Gesamtwert				Ungewichteter Gesamtwert			
		35/160				38/160				37/160			
		Gewichteter Gesamtwert				Gewichteter Gesamtwert				Gewichteter Gesamtwert			
		1.0303				0.73719				0.97631			
		Ungewichtete Gesamtwertigkeit				Ungewichtete Gesamtwertigkeit				Ungewichtete Gesamtwertigkeit			
		0.30606				0.29091				0.31591			
		Gewichtete Gesamtwertigkeit				Gewichtete Gesamtwertigkeit				Gewichtete Gesamtwertigkeit			
		0.25758				0.1843				0.24408			

Figure 5: Evaluation of concepts

The tool should be used to choose between competitive concepts, although the evaluation of these concepts remains subjective and therefore is prone to error. Nevertheless, the estimated component properties support the decision between competitive concepts and the overall development of component in multi-material-design.

5 CONCLUSIONS

Multi-material-design is a promising approach to an economic and sustainable lightweight design for automotive applications in large-scale production. Ecology, lightweight design and economy are conflicting development goals, thus compromises and an assessment of the ecological, economical, and lightweight properties are compulsory. In addition to these approaches, various component concepts must be taken into consideration as well. It must be remembered that the component properties are depending on each other, causing a high complexity for the designing engineer. The best method to manage this complexity is a software tool that determines the properties and enables the user to compare various component concepts with each other. This tool contains empirical and analytical formula, which estimate the mentioned properties and various evaluation methods to compare the concepts.

The MATLAB-based tool for component evaluation will be extended by further analytical and empirical calculation modules. Additionally a coupling of parametric CAD models and the possibility of pareto optimisation of component concepts regarding competing development goals will be sought.

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